

The Mathematical Evolution of Dimensionless Physical Constants

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the coupling constants for the fundamental forces are calculated by considering volume of 4-dimensional space time sphere. Firstly, the fine structure constant is calculated by considering volume of 4-dimensional space time sphere. In addition, the fine structure constant at high energy is evaluated by using the fine structure constant formula. Moreover, the relationship of electro-weak and strong force coupling constant equation is developed to unify the electronuclear force. Furthermore, more accurate value of proton-to-electron mass ratio is evaluated.

Keywords: Volume of sphere, fine structure constant, fine structure constant at high energy, strong force coupling constant, proton-to-electron mass ratio

Theoretical Formulae for the Dimensionless Fundamental Physical Constants and its Calculation

- I. The simple formula for the relativistic splits of the atomic spectral lines of the fine structure constant can be expressed as

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{\left[\left(\frac{3}{2} \right)^3 \times \beta_0 \right]^2 \times \sqrt{\pi}}{\left[2 \times \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi \right)^3 \right]^2} \quad (1)$$

In the above Eq. (1), α^2 is equivalent to the ratio of the electron potential energy of the first circular orbit of the Bohr atomic model and the energy equivalent to the electron mass. The numerator term in right hand side of the Eq. (1), $\sqrt{\pi}$ is the Gaussian integral where infinite sphere is continuously expanding with finite sphere. Now solving Eq. (1) for the fine structure constant, α , is equivalent to the ratio between the energy needed to overcome the electrostatic repulsion driving these electrons apart and the energy of a single photon of angular wavelength.

$$\alpha = \frac{\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^3 \times \pi^{1/4} \times \beta_0}{2 \times \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi\right)^3} = 0.00729735256... = \frac{1}{137.03599958..} \quad (2)$$

where $\beta_0 = \sqrt{1 - (\alpha_0)^2}$ [1] is based on the Einstein special relativity theory. Here, π (3.14159265359...) and $\alpha_0^{-1} = \frac{360}{\phi^2}$ (137.5077640504...) is the Bohr approximation [2] for the fine structure constant while considering the golden angle. When free electron recombines with hydrogen nuclei, the electron cascade down the energy levels, emitting photon is represented by the volume of sphere in the denominator term in the right hand side of Eq. (2). Here 2 represent the cascading of electron from one energy level to another energy level in the atomic model.

II. From Eq. (2), the fine structure constant at high energy, $\alpha(m_z)$, can be expressed as

$$\alpha(m_z) = \frac{\alpha \times 2\pi \times \left[\frac{2}{3}\right]^3}{\sqrt{3}} = \frac{1}{127.493841848..} \quad (3)$$

The term in right hand side of the Eq. (3) can be considered as multiple of fine structure constant and Higgs field potential circumference. $\sqrt{3}$, can be explained as 3 W^\pm and Z boson with line joining at some distance in the Mexican hat shaped potential. The calculated value of fine structure constant at high energy in Eq. (3) is approximately equal to the value reported in the reference. ^[3]

III. The strong force coupling constant, $\alpha_s(m_Z)$, can be related to electroweak force (Eq. 3) and can be expressed as

$$\alpha_s(m_Z) = \frac{1}{\alpha(m_Z)} \times \frac{Degree}{3 \times 360^\circ} = 0.1180498534.. \quad (4)$$

When 3 pi-meson rotated 360° in the potential produces 3 W^\pm and Z boson particles. The calculated value of the strong force coupling constant, $\alpha_s(m_Z)$, in Eq. (4) is approximately equal to the value reported in the reference. ^[4]

IV. Lenz ^[5] formula agreed remarkably well with the proton-to-electron mass ratio. To

explain its formula, the proton-to-electron mass ratio, $\frac{m_p}{m_e}$, can be expressed as

$$\frac{m_p}{m_e} = 3 \times 2\pi \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^4 \times \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{4}{3}\pi\right)^3 = 6\pi^5 = 1836.1181871.. \quad (5)$$

The above Eq. (5) is the multiples of volume of sphere of electron, 3 represents the elementary particles (electron, proton and neutron) interaction under the relativistic circumference effect. To get more accurate result of proton-to-electron mass ratio, divide above Eq. (5) by the relativistic effect

$$\frac{m_p}{m_e} = \frac{6\pi^5}{\beta_0} = 1836.1666664... \quad (6)$$

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